

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF COACHES ON LEADING TO SUCCESSFUL STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION

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Lived Experiences of Coaches on Leading to Successful Strategy Implementation

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Abstract

The purpose of this qualitative study was to know the coping mechanisms of coaches in strategy and tactic implementation from the perspective of the coaches. Furthermore, to investigate the importance of communication and coaching dynamics, The researcher used phenomenology approach to gain understanding of the human behaviors through the eyes of the participants. The study included five participants who were purposely selected for in-depth interviews. Thematic analysis in phenomenology were used to analyze the data in this study. This study is anchored on the theory of Humanism by Abraham Maslow (1938) it is an educational theory that places learner at the center of the educational experiences. Once the data collection is complete, all interviews were thematically identified and categorized into two themes. The following topics were identified as themes: 1) coping mechanism of coaches, 2) Importance of communication and dynamics, these were the most prominent themes that emerged from coaches' experiences in strategies and tactics implementation. Game strategy and tactics are indispensable elements in the realm of games, serving as the guiding principles and practical maneuvers that lead players to victory. The study recommends implementing strategies such as emotional intelligence training, resilience-building workshops, fostering open communication channels, encouraging flexibility in game plans, and promoting team cohesion to address coaches' struggles effectively. These recommendations aim to enhance coaches' abilities, leading to improved team performance and a more fulfilling coaching experience.

Keywords: *strategy and tactic, coaches, lived experiences*

Introduction

Game strategies and tactics involve deliberate decisions and actions by players to achieve specific objectives within a game. Kraaijenbrink (2021) found out that implementation of strategies and tactics can face several challenges that hinder successful execution. Common problems include ineffective communication, inadequate alignment, resistance to change, resource constraints, poor accountability, lack of clear goals, and insufficient planning and control. These issues can lead to misalignment, confusion, lack of commitment, wasted resources, and ultimately, failure in executing strategies effectively

In the UK, the demanding nature of achieving top athletic performance, emphasizing the essential elements of time, commitment, and meticulously planned training. It underscores the critical importance of effectively managing stress and ensuring optimal adaptation to training to support the development and success of high-performance student-athletes (Gomez et al., 2018).

In the Albay, imbalance in leadership styles exhibited by swimming coaches in the region is one of the key issues they face. Training and instruction behavior is noted as a strength among coaches and there is a lack of practice in democratic and autocratic coaching styles. This disparity in leadership approaches can impact the

effectiveness of coaching and the overall development of athletes. Additionally, It emphasizes the importance of effective communication, particularly through positive feedback, to motivate athletes, enhance performance, and maintain a positive coach-athlete relationship. Furthermore, it identifies various challenges faced by swimming coaches in Albay, such as the need for immediate action on issues like democratic autocratic behavior, training behavior, social support, and positive feedback. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving coaching effectiveness and athlete development in the region (Labarda, 2021).

In Tagum City, coaching behavior significantly influences athlete satisfaction. Domains such as physical training and conditioning, technical skills, goal setting, competition strategies, and personal rapport were identified as predictors of athlete satisfaction. However, the domain of mental preparation did not significantly predict athlete satisfaction. The importance of various domains of coaching behavior in determining athlete satisfaction, emphasizing the significance of factors like physical training, technical skills, goal setting, competition strategies, and personal rapport in enhancing athlete satisfaction levels (Belleza, 2021).

Despite the increasing emphasis on coaching studies, there is still insufficient exploration of how cultural and contextual factors influence coaching practices. Current research often overlooks how societal norms and cultural diversity within teams affect coaching approaches. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for adapting strategies to diverse environments and fostering inclusive team cultures. Urgent longitudinal research is needed to assess the long-term effects of coaching strategies on athlete development and well-being. Addressing these gaps promptly can improve coaching effectiveness and support tailored interventions prioritizing athlete well-being.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences of selected coaches on leading to successful strategy implementation.

Specifically, this study sought answer to the question:

1. What are the lived experiences of coaches on leading to successful strategy implementation?

Methodology

This qualitative research study will utilize a descriptive comparative approach. According to Tenny et al. (2022), qualitative research gathers participants' experiences, perceptions, and behavior. It answers the hows and whys instead of how many or how much. Phenomenology is a type of qualitative research focused on gaining an understanding of the human behaviors through the eyes of the participants in the study. Phenomenology is inspired by the phenomenon of human consciousness and is a reflective analysis of the life-world experiences (Jordan M. 2019). In context with this study, the researcher will use this to know the coaches implementation of game strategies and tactics.

In addition, This study will be conducted within the private schools of institution renowned for their excellence in education services in Davao City. The respondents of the study will consist of five coaches of private schools within Davao City. The gathered data will be analyzed with the use of thematic analysis. According to (Dawati, 2020), Thematic analysis is a qualitative research method that researchers use to systematically organize and analyse complex data sets. It is a search for themes that can capture the narratives available in the account of data sets.

Results and Discussion

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From the data gathered, there were two significant themes on the lived experiences of coaches on leading successful strategy implementation I extracted from the focused group discussion and in-depth interview. Both these themes emerged from critical reflection. These are the coping mechanisms of coaches and unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics.

Figure 1. *Emerging Themes on coaches lived experiences on strategy and tactic implement*

During interviews, coaches revealed a recurring struggle with their coping mechanism as coaches and unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics. Under the roof of coping mechanism of coaches, two sub-themes emerged: coping strategy of coaches on the athletes' emotion and behaviors and negotiating setbacks in planning, assessment, and motivation. On the latter part, two sub-themes emerged as well under the unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics: Adjusting game plans, strategies, and tactics during and after matches and maneuvering complications in coaching dynamics

Coping Mechanism of Coaches

As a teacher, I experience a lot of challenges within my profession, making different and multifaceted coping mechanism. Social support emerges as a fundamental strategy, enabling us teachers to seek guidance and share experiences with colleagues and mentors. Mindfulness practices, including deep breathing exercises, are commonly utilized to manage stress and maintain focus amidst high pressure scenarios. Compas et al. (2017) and Lazarus & Folkman (2014) state that coping mechanisms have been defined consistently as the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies individuals use to manage stressors and challenges in their lives. These

mechanisms are essential for maintaining psychological well-being and resilience in the face of adversity.

Coping strategy of Coaches on the athletes' emotions and behaviors.

With my perspective as an interviewer, I sensed that managing athletes emotion and behavior is crucial. The approach must emphasize empathy, communication and self-awareness. Prioritizing building of trust, maintaining open discussion and setting boundaries to create a supportive environment. Celebrating athletes successes reinforces positive behavior and foster a positive team culture. To wit, some of the participants had expressed:

...give feedback on those interactions with their teammates inside and outside of the court, as well as how they interact with you as their coach and try to assess whether how what are the things that you need to Let go or attitude that they need to let go and how will they improve the attitude towards their teammates and, of course, towards your coach or towards their coach during the game. P4, IDI L144-150

In the interviews, it has become apparent that dealing with behaviors and emotions is one way to know your athletes better. Coaches expressed how these varied encounters contribute significantly to the development of a profound understanding of their players and their behaviors. The statement supports Jowett and Cockerill (2003) that coaches prioritize building strong relationships with their athletes based on trust, respect, and genuine care. By demonstrating consistency, integrity, and empathy, coaches establish a foundation of trust that encourages athletes to confide in them and seek guidance when needed. This trust allows coaches to address athletes' emotions and behaviors in a supportive and constructive manner, fostering a positive team dynamic.

Negotiating Setbacks in Planning, Assessment, and Motivation.

From the observers' standpoint, it points to the coach's dedication to holistic development of their athletes. Based on their narration, I observed that coaches actively engaged in adapting strategies, reassessing, and seeking alternative approaches to achieve desired outcomes. Embracing setbacks as opportunities for growth, individuals can adapt their strategies, seek feedback, and stay motivated in pursuit of their goals. Ultimately, navigating setbacks effectively can lead to greater resilience, success, and personal fulfillment.

...adapting to athletes needs involves, number one, personalized assessment, communication, and even training plans. Of course, included na po dira ang flexibility, ang motivational support, ang continuous na evaluation, so empathy as well, and professional development may enhance coaching effectiveness. P2, IDI L76-80

The statement supports Yeager et al. (2012). Negotiating setbacks in planning, assessment, and motivation involves acknowledging challenges, adapting strategies, and maintaining resilience. It is about reframing setbacks as opportunities for growth, adjusting goals as needed, seeking support from peers or mentors, and staying focused on long-term objectives.

Unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics.

As I explore the importance of communication and coaching dynamics, I'm fascinated by how the way we talk and interact affects coaching outcomes. By studying how coaches give feedback, motivate people, and build relationships, I hope to understand what makes coaching successful. My goal is to find practical tips that coaches can use to communicate better and make coaching experiences more effective for personal and professional growth. Grant (2013) states that understanding communication and coaching dynamics is crucial for achieving desired outcomes. Hargrove (2011) further emphasizes the impact of effective communication and coaching interactions on personal and professional growth. Additionally, Anderson and Oliver (1987) highlight the significance of behavior-based salesforce control systems in optimizing coaching dynamics. Moreover, Kegan and Lahey (2009) underscore the importance of overcoming immunity to change through effective communication and coaching strategies.

Adjusting game plans, strategies, and tactics during and after matches.

In my role as an interpreter, I interpret this perspective, emphasizing the significance of analyzing past games and learning to adapt during difficult situations helps both players and coaches to be calm and handle pressure. As I have observed during interview, it seems that sudden changes in the direction of the momentum of the match can change the effectiveness of the game plan. During the game, strategies and tactics can change significantly and make the teams plan less effective. It can disrupt the team's carefully laid-out plans. This disruption requires quick adaptation and adjustments to regain control of the game or exploit new opportunities. After the match, teams conduct a thorough analysis of the game to understand the impact of steering reversals on their performance. They review their game plans, strategies, and tactics to identify what worked well and what didn't. This post-match analysis helps teams learn from their experiences, pinpoint areas for improvement, and adjust their approach for future matches.

We try to check... Um... What are the...What are the weaknesses that we had during a game. Especially if it's a game that we've lost. We would try to assess if... What are the better strategies next time. What's going to be...What are the things that we have to improve. And what are the things that we have to retain. P1, IDI L202-207

...So we have the post-match analysis. After that, we will be having a feedback from our players and of course, opponent's analysis, experiment and innovation. And the last is the continuous learning and adaptation. So by taking a comprehensive and proactive approach to evaluating our game strategy and tactics, I can identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments and

ensure that we are always striving to perform at our best on our field. P3, IDI L291-299

Further, the statement supports Lames et al. (2007) that when teams encounter unexpected challenges or changes in the flow of the game, they often need to make quick adjustments to their tactics and strategies. These in-game adaptations can be the difference between success and failure, allowing teams to capitalize on opportunities or mitigate threats in real-time. In addition, a team's ability to pivot and change its game plan in response to evolving circumstances is a hallmark of strategic flexibility. In addition Grant (2019) states that flexibility enables teams to maintain a competitive edge, as they can adjust their tactics to exploit weaknesses in the opponent's strategy or adapt to changes in the game environment .

Maneuvering complications in coaching dynamics.

Through interviews I've learned that coaching involves navigating challenges like balancing authority and collaboration, resolving conflicts, adapting coaching strategies to individual athletes, and managing external pressures. Coaches must maintain effective communication, interpersonal skills, and adaptability to foster a positive environment for athlete development and team success.

...continuous monitoring and evaluation of progress can help identify issues early on and allowing for timely adjustments to ensure a successful strategy. P3, IDI L99-101

...evaluating our game strategy and tactics is very important. It is a continuous process that involves careful observation, analysis, and reflection. P3, IDI L290-292

The statement supports Kline (2015) facilitating self-reflection helps coaches gain insight into their challenges, strengths, and opportunities for growth. Coaches can use reflective questioning techniques to stimulate deeper thinking and promote self-awareness. In addition, Berger (2018) acknowledged that coaching is not a one-size-fits-all approach and is willing to adapt strategies and techniques to meet the unique needs of each coachee . This flexibility allows coaches to respond effectively to unexpected challenges or changes in the coaching process by integrating these strategies into their coaching practice, coaches can navigate the complexities of coaching dynamics more effectively.

Conclusions

During interviews, coaches revealed a recurring struggle with their coping mechanism as coaches and unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics. Under the roof of coping mechanism of coaches, two sub-themes emerged: coping strategy of coaches on the athletes' emotion and behaviors and negotiating setbacks in planning, assessment, and motivation. On the latter part, two sub-themes emerged as well under the unveiling the importance of communication and dynamics: steering reversals on the effectivity of game plans, strategies and tactics during and post match and maneuvering complications in coaching dynamics

In addressing the recurring struggles of coaches with coping mechanisms and the importance of effective communication and dynamics, it's imperative to implement comprehensive strategies. Coaches can benefit greatly from initiatives aimed at enhancing their emotional intelligence, resilience, and communication skills. Based on the identified themes and sub-themes, it's clear that coaches face significant challenges related to coping mechanisms and communication dynamics. Here are some recommendations:

Implement Emotional Intelligence Training: Coaches should undergo training in emotional intelligence to better cope with athletes' emotions and behaviors. This can involve techniques for managing stress, empathy-building exercises, and understanding the psychological factors influencing athlete performance.

Develop Resilience Building Workshops: Coaches need to develop resilience to negotiate setbacks effectively. Workshops or seminars focusing on resilience-building strategies can equip coaches with the tools to bounce back from failures, adapt their plans, and stay motivated in the face of challenges.

Foster Open Communication Channels: Establishing open communication channels between coaches and athletes is crucial. Regular team meetings, one-on-one discussions, and feedback sessions can facilitate constructive dialogue and address any issues or concerns that may arise.

Encourage Flexibility in Game Plans: Coaches should be encouraged to embrace flexibility in their game plans, strategies, and tactics. This involves being open to adjustments during matches and post-match analyses based on the evolving dynamics of the game and the team's performance.

Promote Team Cohesion: Building strong team dynamics is essential for effective coaching. Coaches should focus on fostering a sense of unity among team members, encouraging collaboration, trust, and mutual respect. Team-building activities and exercises can help strengthen these bonds.

Provide Conflict Resolution Training: Maneuvering complications in coaching dynamics often involves navigating conflicts effectively. Offering training in conflict resolution techniques can empower coaches to address interpersonal conflicts within the team and maintain a positive coaching environment.

Offer Continuous Professional Development: Continuous learning is key for coaches to stay updated on best practices and emerging

trends in coaching. Providing opportunities for ongoing professional development through workshops, conferences, and online courses can enhance coaches' skills and knowledge base.

By implementing these recommendations, coaches can better cope with challenges related to athlete emotions, setbacks in planning, communication dynamics, and effectiveness in game strategies, ultimately leading to improved team performance and a more fulfilling coaching experience.

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